

Book Review: Fundamentals of Airline Marketing

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Article Info	Abstract
REVIEW ARTICLE	<p>"Fundamentals of Airline Marketing" is a comprehensive exploration of the complex field of airline marketing within the ever-evolving aviation industry. Authored by experts in the field, the book navigates through crucial dimensions such as airline strategy, global influences, digital marketing, market segmentation, and customer experience management. The book strategically integrates international case studies at the end of each chapter, offering readers a real-time lens into the challenges and innovations shaping the contemporary aviation industry. The book balances theoretical frameworks with practical insights, providing actionable strategies grounded in the industry's current realities. Especially, the inclusion of the Covid-19 pandemic underscores the book's timely relevance, positioning it as a resource for navigating uncertainties in the dynamic aviation landscape. This review underscores the book's academic rigor, practical applicability, and its significance for academics, students, and practitioners engaged in the evolving world of aviation development. "Fundamentals of Airline Marketing" emerges as an essential guide for understanding the multifaceted perspective of airline marketing within the global aviation environment.</p>
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Fundamentals of Airline Marketing
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The field of airline marketing represents a vast and dynamic domain within the aviation industry. The multifaceted nature of this field encompasses a wide range of strategic, operational, and consumer-centric considerations, rendering it a subject of perpetual evolution (Shaw, 2016). As airlines navigate a complex landscape influenced by technological advancements, shifting consumer behaviors, and global economic trends, the study of airline marketing emerges as a pivotal field for academic exploration. "Fundamentals of Airline Marketing," authored by Scott Ambrose and Blaise Waguespack and published by Routledge in 2021 as part of the series "Aviation Fundamentals" takes on the challenge of dissecting this complex subject matter, providing readers with a scholarly foundation to comprehend the complex interplay of factors that shape marketing strategies within the airline sector. The aviation industry, being a multifaceted and ever-changing industry, experiences continuous transformative changes impacted by a multitude of variables, spanning from global economic pressures to advancements in technology (Doganis, 2009). The book provides a thorough

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examination of diverse elements that mold the present-day environment of airline operations. In order to give readers a comprehensive understanding of the strategic frameworks that influence decision-making in the aviation industry, the authentic component of the literature delves into the intricacies of airline strategy and organization. The first part of the book, within this framework, walks readers through the complexities of airline organization and strategy, giving them a thorough grasp of the strategic frameworks that guide decision-making in the airline sector. The chapter emphasizes the concept of disruptive innovation, as proposed by Clayton Christensen (2003), as a way to clarify the evolution of airline business models. It suggests that successful airlines often begin their operations in the low-cost segment of Porter's Matrix (1985), introducing products that may be considered inferior but are attractively priced, thus expanding the lower tier of the market. This disruptive entry stimulates new demand without initially infringing on the existing market share. Gradually, as disruptive airlines develop superior products, they move upstream, challenging industry incumbents. The case of Southwest Airlines exemplifies this pattern, starting as a leader in low-cost air travel, convincing new passengers to choose air transportation with significantly low fares, and subsequently transitioning into a hybrid position along the continuum. The theory of disruptive innovation offers a compelling framework for understanding the transformative dynamics within the airline industry, where startups often disrupt established players by strategically positioning themselves in the market (Chapter 1). As airlines operate within a globalized framework, the second chapter meticulously examines the multitude of factors that shape their operational environment. This examination sheds light on the intricate interplay of geopolitical, economic, and regulatory dynamics. Moreover, this chapter underscores the increasing significance of environmental considerations within the aviation industry. The expression of disapproval towards air travel is shown as exemplified by the "flight shaming" movement in Scandinavia's (Whyte, 2019) technological aspects, championing a holistic approach to cultivating a sustainable airline ecosystem (Chapter 2). In the era of digitalization, the third chapter delves into the pivotal role of technology in airline digital marketing. It unravels the tactics employed by airlines to maintain competitiveness in an ever-expanding digital landscape. The intricate interaction between digital marketing strategies and each phase of the travel cycle is shown, with particular emphasis on the critical role of technology in shaping customer interactions and influencing decision-making processes. This extensive perspective positions the chapter as a valuable resource for comprehending the evolving landscape of airline marketing in the era of extensive data and digital transformation (Chapter 3). In the fourth chapter, a demonstration is presented to elucidate the distinctions between customers and consumers just like in the case study of Southwest Airlines (Petzinger, 1996). This insight into the multifaceted motivations of customers and consumers provides valuable perspectives on tailoring methodologies for different segments within a given market. This case study contributes to the scholarly discourse on effective marketing strategies that navigate the complexities of consumer behavior and preferences (Chapter 4). The fifth chapter delves deeply into the intricate landscape of defining airline offerings, utilizing the airline product model. The airline industry encompasses a wide range of products, including essential, supplementary, and emblematic/experiential elements. The case study of Turkish Airlines (Nigam, 2016) in this chapter highlights its strategic utilization of the enhanced airline product model, leveraging its extensive global network of routes as a distinctive product characteristic. Importantly, the chapter emphasizes the expanded perspective on passenger air travel and assesses the substantial value for airlines, as well as potential opportunities for revenue growth (Chapter 5).

The sixth chapter which is the second part of the book presents a comprehensive analysis of the notion of "place," primarily focusing on distribution channels rather than physical locations. The chapter specifically examines its unique application within the airline industry. Besides, the chapter explores the evolving structure of digital innovations, including metasearch and recent advancements like New Distribution Capability (NDC) and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). However, notwithstanding the comprehensive examination conducted in this chapter on the intricate channel structure within the airline sector, it may be deemed a chapter wherein the flow decelerates amidst the book (Chapter 6). The seventh chapter of the book focuses heavily on the vital role of effective branding and promotion in the airline industry, thus highlighting its significance in the highly competitive global arena. The chapter stresses that successful branding is not limited to Full-Service Network Carriers (FSNCs) only, as there are several Low-Cost Carriers (LCCs) that demonstrate profitable operations and strong brands. Additionally, the chapter underscores the importance of clear, consistent, and persuasive communication through integrated marketing across both traditional and digital platforms. Specifically, it explores the implicit industry norm of refraining from overtly promoting safety track records, which raises questions about the challenges airlines face when directly addressing safety in their advertising. Despite safety being a critical and anticipated aspect of airline operations, the authors acknowledge the necessity of striking a balance between indirectly conveying safety and addressing passengers' fears and

concerns (Chapter 7). The eighth chapter presents a comprehensive examination of the development of airline pricing strategies, tracing the shift from cost-based to competition-based and ultimately customer-value-based approaches. The authors emphasize the crucial importance of understanding customer perceptions of value, while also recognizing the complex pricing landscape influenced by macroeconomic factors. Additionally, the chapter investigates the significant growth of ancillary revenues, illustrating the industry's expansion beyond traditional ticket sales to include various travel-related products and services. Another noteworthy point in the chapter is to explore the legal ramifications of price fixing, focusing specifically on the investigation into major U.S. airlines in 2015 for suspected collusion to raise ticket prices. The inclusion of the historical anecdote involving Robert Crandall (New York Times, 1983; Petzinger, 1996), the CEO of American Airlines, who was accused of price fixing during a contentious price war, emphasizes the caution against engaging in discussions about prices with competitors (Chapter 8). The authors allocate a significant portion of the book to the examination of airline services, internal marketing, and human resources management in the ninth chapter, acknowledging the crucial role that human capital plays in ensuring operational excellence. Within this chapter, an in-depth exploration is conducted into the intricate dynamics of how labor unions shape the operations of U.S. full-service network carriers within the airline industry. Furthermore, the section delves into the examination of the dynamic landscape that arises from technical progress and the labor-intensive character of the aviation industry, specifically in light of the Covid-19 pandemic. It highlights also the enduring significance of addressing the challenges posed by high unionization through strategic internal marketing and human resources management (Chapter 9). The final chapter presents a comprehensive methodology for assessing and handling the customer experience, highlighting the importance of measuring service quality in the highly competitive airline industry. This chapter explores the intricate landscape of service failures within the airline sector, shedding light on the numerous challenges faced by airline managers in their operational pursuits. By dissecting various factors such as labor constraints, government policies, safety protocols, weather conditions, and the complexities of airport operations, the chapter underscores the necessity of employing service recovery strategies to effectively address customer dissatisfaction. The chapter's focus on the transformative potential of service recovery, the intricacies of fairness in the recovery process, and proactive measures to mitigate complaints positions it as a valuable resource for researchers, professionals, and stakeholders navigating the ever-changing domain of airline service quality (Chapter 10).

Each case study at the end of the chapter, meticulously curated and analyzed, serves as a microcosm of the aviation industry's multifaceted landscape, capturing the essence of strategic decision-making, market dynamics, and the innovative approaches adopted by airlines in response to industry shifts. The book thus becomes a repository of practical knowledge, enhancing the learning experience for academics and students alike while simultaneously providing practitioners with actionable insights that are directly translatable to their operational contexts. Furthermore, the inclusion of case studies at the forefront of aviation's dynamic developments, such as responses to the Covid-19 pandemic, underscores the book's timely relevance. This not only equips readers with a nuanced understanding of how airlines adapt to unforeseen challenges but also positions the book as an important resource for navigating the uncertainties inherent in the contemporary aviation landscape.

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